

LONG TERM STRENGTH OF GLASS REINFORCED PLASTICS IN WET ENVIRONMENTS

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Data are presented on the long term strength under sustained static (and in some cases cyclic) loading of bundles of E-glass, Cemfil, Kevlar and Carbon fibres immersed in water and also under ambient laboratory conditions. The effect of resin impregnation of the fibre bundles is also examined. Measurements of slow crack growth rates obtained by fracture mechanics methods on sheet E-glass and Cemfil glass are then described and finally a theory of bundle failure by stress corrosion is developed whereby the time to failure may be predicted from a knowledge of the crack growth law and appropriate Weibull parameters.

1. INTRODUCTION

Although highly sophisticated methods for design with composite materials have been developed these are usually based on the short term materials properties. It is only recently that attention has been directed towards environmental degradation. The reasons are twofold; firstly the loss of strength under wet conditions, at least with glass reinforced plastics, has been largely obscured in the past by the inevitable over design in terms of strength in order to provide the necessary stiffness. Secondly there is no scientific basis for accelerated testing or extrapolation of medium term results so lengthy research programmes and extensive test facilities are required. Much of the previous work has therefore been restricted to environmental exposure followed by mechanical testing and in the few instances where the load and environment have been applied simultaneously the specimens have usually been tested in flexure, so that interpretation is complicated by the need to consider both non uniform stress and non uniform permeation by moisture. Nevertheless it is established, at least qualitatively, that GRP can be severely weakened in the presence of moisture - for a review see A. F. Johnson (1) - and it is of interest to consider possible causes. It is well known that bulk glass is susceptible to stress corrosion in the presence of water or water vapour. In water the crack velocity is proportional to the stress intensity factor K_1^n where n is dependent on glass composition, and for borosilicate glass is of the order of 16 (2). The strength of E - glass fibres is therefore expected to be time dependent in the presence of quite small amounts of moisture and there is some evidence to this effect in the literature (3) - (4). The polyester component of GRP is also subject to water attack; when the resin is free from inorganic impurities the water merely acts as a swelling agent and plasticises the resin but if it contains traces of salts the resin can act as a semi-permeable membrane and the resulting osmotic pressure within the resin leads to cracking (5). Thus when E - glass fibres which may give rise to alkaline hydrolysis products are embedded in a polyester resin (usually producing acid hydrolysis products) the interface will tend to become more hydrophilic and three distinct but interrelated effects may be predicted:-

- (1) the individual fibres will be weakened as a result of crack growth promoted by water which has penetrated the resin
- (2) resin swelling will produce a radial stress at the interface which will be reinforced by osmotic entry of water and lead to fibre debonding, increase in transfer length and consequent weakening of the composite
- (3) plasticisation of the resin by water will result in increased visco-elasticity and a further (time dependent) increase in transfer length.

In addition the gel coat, on the surface of a g.r.p. article, may act as a semi-permeable membrane between water and the polar fibre-matrix interface, and so give rise to osmotic blistering.

In this paper we present evidence that the first mechanism is the dominant one, and we develop a theory of bundle failure by stress corrosion that accounts satisfactorily for the stress rupture results of the unimpregnated strands.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Tensile testing of Unidirectional GRP coupons requires careful specimen preparation in order to avoid failure in the grips or longitudinal splitting and it was clearly out of the question to use such specimens in the present study which requires a large number of specimens. It was therefore decided to use resin impregnated strands (ie. bundles of single filaments - 400 in the case of E - glass) which apart from ease of gripping have the added advantage, on account of their

small cross sections, of reaching equilibrium with the environment more rapidly.

Strands were impregnated with either polyester (Crystic 189 LV plus 2% powder catalyst B, Scott Bader & Co. Ltd.) or epoxy (Ciba-Geigy MY 750 + 10% HY951) resin by drawing them continuously through a resin bath into a vertical tubular oven at 120°C for the epoxy and 145°C for the polyester at a rate to give a residence time of 3 min. The ends of the test specimens (gauge length 50cm) were potted in the appropriate resin and the top attached to a loading jack and the bottom to a weight. Time to failure was recorded electronically. In the fatigue experiment the top of the strand was attached to a crank/slider arrangement which lifted the weight via the fibre strand to produce a square wave stress cycle. The strand was maintained under slight tension throughout the cycle by a take-up spring.

Details of the fibres are given in the table. All the fibres were tested in the form of unimpregnated strands. In addition the E-glass (which will have been sized) was impregnated with both polyester and epoxy and the carbon with polyester only. Fibre volume fraction in the impregnated strands was approximately 0.5.

The technique, and equation (1) of Wiederhorn (2) were used to measure crack velocity as a function of K for bulk glass. The temperature was 22°C.

Fibre	Supplier	density (Kg m ⁻³ x 10 ³)	total fibre cross ₂ section in strand (cm ²)
E-glass ECR 328	T.B.A. Industrial Products	2.54	5.64 x 10 ⁻⁴
Cemfil glass	Pilkington Bros.	2.71	2.83 x 10 ⁻⁴
Carbon T 300-1000	Toray Industries	1.9	3.5 x 10 ⁻⁴
Kevlar 49	Du Pont	1.45	3.06 x 10 ⁻⁴

3. RESULTS

3.1. Carbon

Before we consider the glass fibre results it is of interest to look at the behaviour of carbon which may be considered inert to water so that any reduction in strength must depend solely on the properties of the matrix or interface. In the absence of any fibre degradation we expect the uncoupled strand to either break immediately on loading or to last indefinitely. This was generally observed, although a few specimens did in fact break in a finite time (Fig.1); the stress rupture curve remains essentially horizontal. The impregnated strands, Δ in Figure 1, differ in two respects: firstly the short term strength is much higher, which of course is expected as a broken fibre is only unloaded over a small distance either side of the break so that most of the fibre remains loaded, and secondly there is a small but definite reduction in strength with time. In an extension of Rosen's theory (6) to take account of a time dependent stress transfer around the ends of a broken fibre due to visco-elastic effects in the resin Lifshitz and Rotem (7) predict around a ten per cent reduction in strength over four decades of time due to this effect alone, and this is roughly consistent with what we observe.

Fig. 1. Stress rupture results for carbon fibre strands X, Kevlar 49 strands O and carbon fibre strands impregnated with polyester resin Δ , all immersed in distilled water.

3.2. E-glass

Here the situation is very different. Even in 'dry' (actually ambient laboratory) conditions the fall off in strength of the impregnated strands (Fig 2) is more rapid than in the case of carbon.

It is also larger than the decrease in strength predicted from matrix effects alone. The decrease we achieve is comparable to the experimental results of Lifshitz and Rotem for unidirectional glass (which were also below their predicted curve for matrix effects alone). For the unimpregnated strand where the fibres were exposed to atmospheric moisture (Fig.3) the degradation in strength becomes more rapid, and still more so for the totally immersed condition (Fig.4).

Fig.3. Stress rupture of E-glass strands under ambient conditions.

Fig.4. Stress rupture of E-glass strands in distilled water. Curve is calculated using equation (8).

Under slow cycle (0.1Hz) fatigue conditions (Fig.7) the total time to failure under wet conditions for a given load is similar to that under static load (Fig.2) although of course the fatigue specimens will only actually be under load for half the time shown.

Fig.7. Fatigue results for polyester impregnated E-glass strands at 0.1 Hz under ambient (O) and wet (X) conditions.

However bearing in mind that many of the specimens exceeded 10⁶ cycles at a strain which caused failure in some of the static specimens in the same time it appears that any additional reduction in strength as a result of fatigue in unidirectional GRP is quite small.

3.3. Cemfil glass

Cemfil is an alkali resistant glass containing zirconia, developed by Pilkington Bros as a reinforcement for cement. As failure of E-glass strands and unidirectional GRP appeared to be dominated by stress corrosion it seemed logical to test a more chemically resistant glass. As expected its performance in water, relative to E-glass, is much improved. In Fig.8 we have plotted time to failure versus load multiplied by the ratio of the respective cross sectional areas given in the table so that a direct comparison may be made between E-glass (Fig.4) and Cemfil. The load at failure of the unimpregnated strand is seen to be about the same at short times but approximately double that of E-glass for times greater than a year.

Fig. 8. Stress rupture of Cemfil strands in distilled water.

3.4. Kevlar 49

Although not of direct relevance to the present investigations it is worth recording that Kevlar 49 strands under wet conditions (Fig.1) show a modest fall-off in strength with time, with a performance somewhere between that of E-glass and Cemfil.

4. DISCUSSION

2.1. Unimpregnated strands and crack growth measurements

From many previous experiments on glass and other brittle solids (Weiderhorn (2) Evans (8)) and our own crack growth measurements on bulk E-glass and Cemfil (Figs.9 & 10)

Fig.9. Crack growth measurements for sheet E-glass in distilled water. Different symbols refer to different specimens.

we know that flaws grow under the influence of stress intensity with a velocity given by

$$v = \frac{da}{dt} = \alpha K_1^m \quad (1)$$

where a is the flaw length and α and n are constants Equation (1) often holds over

Fig.10. As Fig.9 but Cemfil glass.

several decades of v but at very low v the velocity is sometimes observed to fall rapidly with decrease in K_1 towards a stress corrosion limit. For single bulk specimens Davidge et al (9) have shown that equation (1) can be integrated to provide times to failure, or strength as a function of strain rate. However, for bundles of fibres loaded in parallel the situation is more complex, because as some fibres fail the cracks in those curving must grow under an increasing stress, since the specimen supports a constant load.

To solve this problem we shall assume a Weibull (10) distribution of the strength of the population of fibres in a bundle, in the form that the number of fibres unbroken at stress σ , in a total population of fibres N_0 is

$$N = N_0 \exp - \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 and m are constant. The maximum load which can be supported by a bundle of such fibres is given by

$$F_m = AN_0 \sigma_0 \frac{1}{(em)^{1/m}} \quad (3)$$

where e is the base of the natural logarithm and A is the area of cross section of a fibre.

During the course of a stress rupture test the load on a bundle of fibres F , less than F_m , is given by

$$F = NA\sigma \quad (4)$$

and σ increases as N decreases until the remaining fibres can no longer support the load, and the bundle fails.

We assume that the fibres are characterised by a critical stress intensity factor K_{1c} and that they differ from one another in their initial strength, measured in a short time, because they contain flaws of differing length a . Under a stress σ , suddenly imposed, all fibres with longest flaw lengths equal to or greater than

$$a_c = \left(\frac{K_{1c}}{y\sigma} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where y is a constant, will break. Under a given stress σ , therefore, there is a critical flaw length and flaws can only be shorter than this in any fibre surviving. If a fibre is held under a constant tensile stress in a corrosive environment all flaws of length less than a_c will grow until the longest one attains the value a_c when the fibre immediately fails.

We assume that a growth law of the form of (1) is followed by the flaws in the individual fibres during the test. We further assume that the initial distribution of flaw lengths follows a distribution which gives a Weibull distribution of initial strengths represented by (2); that is to say we assume that the number of fibres in a population N_0 having longest flaws of length less than a is given by

$$N = N_0 \exp - \left(\frac{a_0}{a} \right)^{m/2} \quad (6)$$

where

$$a_0^{1/2} = \frac{K_{1c}}{y\sigma_0} \quad (7)$$

During the course of the stress rupture test, then the cracks in all fibres grow longer and as some fibres fail the stress in those remaining increases and so the flaws in these fibres grow faster and so on, until the bundle fails.

With the above assumptions it can be shown (Kelly and McCartney) (11) that the number of fibres breaking as a function of time is given by the equation

$$\left[\left(\frac{F}{N_0 \sigma_0 A} \right)^{n-2} \left(\frac{N(t)}{N_0} \right) - \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{N(t)}{N_0} \right)^{n-1} \left\{ \ln \frac{N_0}{N(t)} \right\} \frac{n-2}{m} - 1 \right] \frac{1}{N_0} \frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha K_{1c}^{n-2} y^2 \sigma_0^2 \left(\frac{F}{N_0 \sigma_0 A} \right)^n \quad (8)$$

The bundle will fail when $-dN/dt$ becomes very large, ie. when the quantity in square brackets equals zero. If we set the quantity in square brackets equal to zero we obtain the number of fibres remaining N_f just before catastrophic failure of the bundle in terms of the load on the bundle F . The time to failure of the bundle is obtained by numerically integrating equation (8) between the limits of N_f and N_1 the number of fibres remaining unbroken as soon as the load F is initially applied. N_1 is found by solving graphically the transcendental equation which results from (4) when (2) is substituted in order to eliminate σ .

Fig.11 shows a plot of the quantity F/F_m , where F_m is given by (3) against the parameter

$$\log_{10} \left\{ \frac{\alpha}{2} K_{1c}^{n-2} y^2 \sigma_0^2 t_f \right\}$$

where t is the time to failure at load F , for $m = 8$ and various values of n . The corresponding curves for $m = 6$ and $m = 10$ vary by no more than one per cent in F/F_m at any point, and so the time to failure is insensitive to the scatter in the strength of the individual fibres.

Fig.11. Stress rupture curves predicted from equation (8) for various values of n and $m = 8$.

In order to test the theory with the experimental results for E-glass strands shown in Fig.4, we take the short term failure load F as equal to 68.7 N (7kg) and using the experimental value of N_A of $5.64 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^{2m}$ and a value of $m = 8$ for E-glass (Rosen (6)) we obtain $\sigma_o = 1.79 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$ from equation (3). From the least square slope in Fig.9 we obtain $n = 14.6$ and $\log \alpha = -89.3$. Interpolating for this value of n in Fig.11 we find that for $F/F_m = 0.5$,

$$\log_{10} \left\{ \frac{\alpha}{2} K_{lc}^{n-2} y^2 \sigma_o^2 t_f \right\} = 4.5$$

We now fit the experimental curve at this point by taking $t_f = 10^3 \text{ min}$ to obtain a value for the constant $\left\{ \frac{\alpha}{2} K_{lc}^{n-2} y^2 \sigma_o^2 \right\}$ equal to 0.527, which enables the remainder of the curve to be computed. Bearing mind the scatter of the experimental points the fit is very good and is in fact virtually coincidental with the best line that can be drawn through the points. It is noteworthy that use of a value of n differing by more than about 2 from the experimental value for bulk E-glass would produce a significant deviation from the experimental points in Fig.4.

Wiederhorn (12) found that K_{Ic} was insensitive to glass composition for silica, soda-lime and borosilicate glasses and was approximately $7.6 \times 10^5 \text{ N/m}^{3/2}$. Using this value, putting $y = \pi/2$ and taking the experimental value of 0.527 for the constant in curly brackets we obtain a value of $\log v = -91.3$ compared with the least squares intercept of -89.3. The discrepancy, corresponding to an error of only about two per cent in the slope of the line in Fig.9 is clearly within experimental error, and it would appear that the theory can satisfactorily explain the stress rupture results for uncoupled E-glass strands.

It should however be pointed out that a large extrapolation is involved in going from the crack growth rates measured for bulk glass to the rates applicable to fibres. To obtain a rough idea of the growth rates involved for fibres we can take $K_{Ic} = 7.6 \times 10^5 \text{ N/m}^{3/2}$ and short term strength of $1.79 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$ to obtain an initial crack size from equation (5) of $0.07 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. of the order of one per cent of the fibre diameter. By the time the strength has fallen to one third of its value, i.e. in the range 10^5 to 10^6 minutes the crack length will have increased to $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ to give an overall growth rate in the range of 10^{-13} - 10^{-14} m/sec which is outside the range of practical measurement by a factor of around 10^3 . There are clear indications that the $\log v$ versus $\log K_I$ relationship is already departing from linearity at higher velocities than these (see the points marked with arrows in Figs. 9 & 10). The crack growth rate is therefore less than that predicted by equation (1) and so, as expected, the stress corrosion of Cemfil strands is much less than would be predicted from the linear portion of Fig.10, which has a slope much the same as that for E-glass (Fig.9).

4.2. Impregnated strands

The increase in short term strength of E-glass fibres on impregnation with resin stems from the localisation of load shedding to a small distance either side of the break in a fibre - the ineffective length - in this case using equation 24 of Rosen (6) this amounts to a reduction from the length of the unimpregnated strand (50 cm) to about 0.1 mm or of the order of one hundred fibre diameters, which is reasonable. Less understandable is the fact that the long term strength decreases to a value approaching that of the unimpregnated strand: this requires an increase in transfer length to a value comparable with the overall length of the specimen, which is surprising, if true. Moreover a very large increase in transfer length should be associated with a very uneven or brush-like fracture surface. No such surface was observed. The explanation may lie in the high value of the exponent n in the crack growth equation. For a hexagonal fibre array a broken fibre will cause a stress concentration of at least $7/6$ over a distance close to the break in adjacent fibres, and a flaw in this region will grow faster than a flaw remote from the break by a factor of $(7/6)^n$, or about ten times as fast for $n = 14.7$. There will thus be a strong tendency for the composite to break with an essentially planar fracture.

4.3. Fatigue

Evans and Fuller (13) have shown that crack propagation in several ceramic materials under cyclic loading is in good agreement with that predicted on the basis of static growth laws - in other words, (in marked contrast to the situation in plastics and metals), there is no enhancement of slow crack growth rate due to cycling. Hence if fatigue of glass fibres under wet conditions is solely due to slow crack growth we should expect the total time under load to failure to be the same under fatigue (square wave) and static loading. For the unimpregnated strand this may not be so in practice due to abrasion between adjacent fibres. We have not tested non-impregnated strands in fatigue. For the impregnated strands, comparison of Fig.5 with Fig.7 shows that the performance is somewhat worse under cyclic loading.

REFERENCES

1. JOHNSON, A. F., Engineering Design Properties of GRP, Brit. Plas.. Fed., Pub; No.215, 1978.
2. WIEDERHORN, S. M. and BOLZ, L. H., J. Amer. Ceram. Soc. , Vol. 53, 1970, pp. 543 - 548.
3. THOMAS, W. F., Physics Chem. Glasses, Vol. 1, 1960, pp. 4 - 18.
4. METCALFE, A. G. and SCHMITZ, G. K., Glass Tech., Vol. 13, 1972, pp. 5 - 16.
5. ASHBEE, K. H. G., FRANK, F. C. and WYATT, R. C. Proc. Roy. Soc., Series A, Vol. 300, 1967, pp. 415 - 419.
6. ROSEN, B. W., AIAA. J., Vol. 2, 1964, pp. 1985 - 1991.
7. LIFSHITZ, J. M. and ROTEM, A., Fibre Sci. and Tech., Vol. 3, 1970, pp. 1 - 20.
8. EVANS, A. G., J. Mat. Sci., Vol. 7, 1972, pp. 1137 - 1146.
9. DAVIDGE, R. W., McLAREN, J. R. and TAPPIN, G., J. Mat. Sci., Vol.8, 1973, pp. 1699 - 1705.
10. WEIBULL, W., J. App. Mech., Vol. 18, 1957, pp. 293 - 297.
11. KELLY, A. and McCARTNEY, L. N., to be published.
12. WIEDERHORN, S. M., J. Amer. Ceram. Soc., Vol. 52, 1969, pp 99 - 109.
13. EVANS, A. G. and FULLER, E. R., Met. Trans., Vol. 5, 1974, pp. 27 - 33.